

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND PUBLIC HEALTH IMPLICATION OF HEAVY METALS IN COMBUSTED COAL AND COAL

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ABSTRACT

Researchers are quite concerned about the concentration of heavy metals as it affects humans and other living organisms. This is especially true of the heavy metals' when present in coal and bottom coal ash. In this study, we compared the levels of heavy metals in coal and bottom coal ash, analyzed the findings and compared the toxicity and utility of the findings, to enhance the understanding of the level of toxicity and utility of certain heavy metals, in order to determine through comparative analysis which of the substance contains the highest level of hazardous heavy metal. Heavy metal concentrations in both substances were measured using an atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS). The results showed that lead had the highest concentration in both materials and that its value was significantly higher than the World Health Organization's (WHO) permissible threshold level. In coal, the concentration was 178.65 mg/kg, or 0.0179%, while in bottom coal ash, or combust coal, it was 160.85 mg/kg, or 0.0161%. These findings indicate that both substances are toxic and environmental pollutant due to their respective values of concentration which is significantly higher than the permissible threshold. The findings indicated that Lead (Pb) is a very toxic substance even at low concentration to living organism had a higher concentration than in coal than in bottom coal ash while other elements were within the WHO permissible value and are of great biological function to living organism. It was observed that the concentration of lead in coal is higher than that of bottom coal ash while other heavy metal had more concentration in bottom coal ash than coal. These findings indicates that coal which has become a major material for cooking and other domestic activities could lead issues of public health concern if efforts are not made to ameliorate the situation

KEY WORDS: *Atomic absorption spectrometer; heavy metal concentration; toxicity; coal and bottom coal ash*

INTRODUCTION

Coal is not classified as a mineral because it is known to have originated from biological sources. As such, it is referred to as a complex geological material, consisting mostly of organic and mineral materials. It is thought to have formed from the remains of dead animals and plants that were exposed to high pressure and temperature for a long time deep beneath the earth's surface. {The way that minerals are used, particularly in combustion, has a big impact on how coal is used. Minerals are also a primary source of elemental coal - as opined by Frankelman; Dai and French (2019) Coal is a non-renewable fossil fuel that is combusted and used to generate electricity. Interestingly both mining technique and combustion process are both hazardous to human, animal and plant health (Afridet' et al 2021). This formed the basis of this study. Furthermore, during mining, burning and other processing activities, the environment may be exposed to the emission of hazardous metal. Also runoff could also carry these heavy metal materials from their primary abode like, the soil, coal or burned coal, into subterranean water and crops. This process, known as the bioaccumulation process, renders them hazardous (Jarup, 2013).

Bottom ash coal is a waste material from coal fired power plant, it is known to contain elements that are potentially toxic at high concentration level when disposed into a land fill (Koech; Everson; Neomagus and Rutto 2015). The main source of coal ash, also known as combusted coal or combust coal residue (CCRs), is the burning of coal in coal-fired power plants. Because bottom ash is too large to be taken up into the smoke stack due to its coarse nature, it is situated at the bottom of the coal furnace (EPA 2023). Heavy metals though occurs naturally but is also present in coal ash in various forms and differs with various geographical regions (Jeff Goodell 2006). Metals with densities more than 5g/cm³ are classified as heavy metals (Jaishankar et' al 2014).

In terms of their toxicity, they can be divided into two classes: micronutrients, such as Mn, Cu, Fe, Zn, Cr, and Ni, which are toxic in small amounts and essential, and non-biologically significant, such as Cd, As, Hg, and Pb, which are persistent in the environment, have a long biological half-life, and can bio-accumulate, making them toxic to living things. Because there are no effective mechanisms for their elimination from human and animal bodies, they have been shown to have negative effects on animals even at low concentrations according to Adah et' al (2006)

The utilization of coal as source of energy has contributed to a chain of ecological and environmental concern through its thermal process of utilization (burning of coal as in coal fired power plant) as averred by Mandal and Senqupta(2006). It is thus important to identify the concentration and level of heavy metal as they could become sources of pollution in the environment leading to public health emergencies.

This study therefore analyzed the concentration of heavy metals in coal and compared with that of combust coal, to ascertain if through bioaccumulation processes they could present issues of toxicity to living organism and ultimately issues of public health concerns.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

STUDY AREA

Coal analyzed for this work was gotten from Zuma 828 coal mining site at Ankpa L.G.A of Kogi-state. Zuma 828 is a mining and exploration company licensed to mine coal from Okobo-Apiko. Okaba coal mine is a surface operating mine in Okaba ,kogi-state. It has a coordinate of (7024'28''N, 7°48'6''E) coordinate. Mindat.org. Its production per ton is about 0.16 million ton per annum.(Global Energy Monitor Wiki 2023). While the bottom coal ash was gotten from Obajana cement plant reject coal site. Obajana is situated in the north central area of Nigeria and it also in the north central area of kogi-state with a coordinate of (709104°N, 64399°E), (Musa D, Kpanache 2014). Obajana cement plant commissioned it's coal mill to power it plant in 2014 to cut operational cost. The company sources it coal source from Enugu and other part of Nigeria including Okaba.

SAMPLE COLLECTION

Some quantity of coal were collectedgotten from Zuma 828 coal mining site at Okaba-Okpiko, Ankpa LGA of Kogi State and sent to the laboratory for analysis. Also, some sample of bottom coal ash were collected from the coal reject at Obajana cement factory, and sent to the laboratory for analysis

ANALYSIS

1 gram of combusted coal was measured into a digestion flask, 200ml of 3:1 of HCl and HNO₃ was added to the same sample and heated in a digestion block for about 1-2 hours at 250°c-350°c, about 2-3ml of H₂O₂ was added to the mixture and it was subjected to heating for another 1hr for complete digestion. The digest obtained after heating was then transferred into a volumetric flask of 50mls and was marked up to the mark with deionized water. The digest sample was analyzed using atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS) for heavy metal analysis through the suction tube. Each of the trace mineral elements was read at their respective wavelengths with their respective hollow cathode lamps using appropriate fuel and oxidant combination. The meter reading for each element was used to calculate for the concentration of each element using the formula bellow .same method was used to analyze the coal which was first grounded to powder before 1 gram was measured into the digest flask.

Ppm or mg/kg (any of the elements) = Meter reading x Slope or Gradient x dilution factor.

%(any of the elements) = ppm or mg/kg divided by 10000 if result is needed in percentage when needed

Calculation

mg/ kg sample = digest conc. x dilution factor

Digest conc. = Analytic reading on AAS

$$\text{dilution factor} = \frac{\text{Vol. of digest} \times \text{aliquot}}{\text{weight of sample}}$$

vol of digest = Final volume of digested or extracted sample

aliquot = ratio of sample to distilled water (when diluted further)

EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

Table showing experimental value gotten from analysis of both coal and combusted coal (bottom coal ash)

S/N	ELEMENTS	Concentration in combusted coal (bottom coal ash) (mg/Kg)	Concentration of coal (mg/Kg)
1	Cadmium Cd	1.150	0.75
2	Lead Pb	160.85	178.65
3	Zinc Zn	20.75	13.35
4	Iron Fe	61.95	8.60
5	Manganese Mn	21.40	2.50
6	Nickel Ni	15.25	6.45
7	Chromium Cr	28.35	13.65
8	Copper Cu	7.65	1.70
9	Cobalt Co	10.20	2.45
10	Magnesium Mg	94.90	89.10

Table 1: The concentration of heavy metals in both coal and combusted coal

Fig. 1: Graphical representation of the concentration of heavy metal in coal and bottom coal ash

RESULT DISCUSSION

From table 1.1 it was discovered that the concentration of heavy metal are higher in combust coal than coal, though the level of lead in coal is far higher than that in combust coal which was an exception and a main finding, as indicated in fig 1. The concentrations of heavy metals are in the following order: Pb> Mg> Cr> Zn> Fe>Ni> Co>Mn> Cu> Cd implying that lead has the highest value and cadmium has the lowest value in term of concentration of heavy metal. Similarly considering the concentration of heavy metal in bottom ash coal, lead has the highest value followed by magnesium and cadmium has the least value it runs in the order Pb> Mg> Fe> Cr> Zn >Mn> Ni> Co> Cu> Cd. The highest value of lead in coal is 178mg/kg while in combusted coal is 160.85mg/kg, the value of cadmium in coal is 0.75mg/kg while in combusted coal is 1.150mg/kg in the experiment conducted. Some variations in concentration of heavy metal were also observed.

The first two most concentrated metals are the same for both substances (lead and magnesium) and the last three elements are also the same for both substances which were cobalt followed by copper and cadmium having the least concentration. Iron has a higher concentration in coal ash than in coal. Considering the high level of concentration of lead which is a very toxic heavy metal even at low concentration, it was observed that the concentration of lead was far higher in both substances than the acceptable permissible level by WHO.

Lead which hardly provides any biological role when consumed, is believed to damage the chlorophyll in plants when in excess. (Zulfiquar et al 2019). Lead is a naturally occurring heavy metal in the crust of the earth, yet even at low concentrations, it is considered dangerous. Lead can harm fetuses and children, impairing their intellectual quotient (IQ) even at low doses as reported by United Nations (1998). On August 11, 2023, a statement was made regarding lead exposure, which can have an impact on several bodily systems and portends great danger especially to children and pregnant women. Though lead exposure at any level has been proven to have negative effects, EARTH REPAIR (2023) indicated that because infants absorb four to five times as much lead as adults do from a given source, they are more susceptible to lead poisoning. Lead sticks to the soil particle and enters drinking water only if the water is acidic and soft, it also enters food chain through consumption of food stuffs and through inhalation. It has been discovered that one third of the daily lead intake occurs through inhalation and two thirds from diet which result in lead accumulation in the body leading to toxicity. It has been reported that adding phosphorous decreases availability of lead to plants, however in some extreme cases, the combination of a lower pH and increased phosphorous concentrations can have adverse impacts on soil microorganisms, (Barrow and Hartemink 2023) thus requiring reinoculation with compost tea and compost later.

The next concentrated heavy metal in both coal and combust coal which is magnesium is an essential heavy metal to both plants and animals, in animals it is responsible for bone formation, reproduction and for normal functioning of the central nervous system. It also plays vital roles in enzyme metabolic system (Aremo; et al 2010). The magnesium concentration level in both coal and combust coal are within the permissible range of greater than 50ppm. Knudsen (1974) and Sankaralingam and Malarvizhi (2020) reported that the critical limit of plant availability of magnesium in soil should be greater than 84mg/kg, implying that the available concentration of magnesium in both samples is within the permissible threshold limit by WHO.

Chromium Cr: Is a naturally occurring element found in rocks, animals, plants, and soil. Though Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry stated that burning coal and petrochemical oils has an impact on its occurrence (Jaishankar et al 2014) nonetheless, the WHO criterion of 100 mg/kg for chromium content indicates that it is within permissible limits (Global energy monitors wiki.2023).

Iron: it is the fourth most abundant element in the earth crust. Iron toxicity is not often discussed in plant science, though it causes severe morphological and physiological disorder in plants, it causes several toxicities to important biomolecules which could lead to ferroptotic cell death and

induced structural changes in photosynthetic system. However, it helps in crop growth even when it is a contaminant (Zahra et al 2021). Levi et al (2024) also opined that it facilitates the oxidation of carbohydrate, protein and fat, contributes to the prevention of anemia and also plays important roles in oxidation during respiration and other functions of the central nervous system. This study revealed that the concentration of iron in both samples is within the permissible level by WHO in soil.

Zinc: It is a naturally occurring metal that can be found in rocks. Animals and plants alike depend on zinc as a trace element. Damage to reproductive organs and mental lethargy are two outcomes of its lack in plants and animals. Its toxicity may cause the mitochondria's ability to produce energy within the cell to be compromised (Bifeng and Xiaoling 2017). At an ideal range of (10–20) µg/g, zinc is crucial for the metabolism of lipids and carbohydrates in plants (Kabata-Pendias, and Pendias, 2010). Though zinc has been reported to disrupt soil processes and lowers microbe activity, which slows down the breakdown of organic matter, only a small number of plants can thrive in zinc-rich soil (Wuana and Okieimen 2011), this study however indicated that zinc is within the range of acceptable value of heavy metals in soil as recommended by WHO which is 300 mg/kg (Christos et al 2018).

Manganese: this is a naturally occurring heavy metal, and the twelfth most abundant heavy metal in the earth's crust. It is very toxic when excessive or abundant with harmful effect to both plant and animal. It enhances the ability of lead to progressively, permanently cause neurological disorder as averred by Andrade et al (2017). It is an essential element for both plant and animal for proper functioning of the body (Maine center for disease and prevention data). Though required in small quantity by plant but like other nutrient Mn is very essential for plant growth (TFI). The concentration observed in this study is within permissible level for soil by WHO which is 100 mg/kg.

Nickel: nickel is found with other element at very low level in the environment. It is available in soil, rocks and volcanic emissions. Nickel induces pathophysiological changes in living system. (Kusalet al 2018) and combines with other element in the soil effectively. Its toxicity depends on the rate of exposure (inhalation, oral or dermal) and solubility of nickel compound. (Reeves, R. and Baker. 2000). All nickel compounds except for metallic nickel have been classified as human carcinogens (Speidel, and Speidel, 2002). The Nickel concentrations observed in this study are within the acceptable threshold.

Cobalt: studies have suggested that cobalt ions affect the growth of *lemna minor* with increase concentration, though excessive cobalt can lead to the occurrence of iron Fe deficiency in young leaves, and could also lead to reduction in the concentration of chlorophyll content (Mahey, et al 2020). For animals, cobalt toxicity can include cardiomyopathy, peripheral neuropathy, vision loss and chronic respiratory disease (Chen, and Lee, 2024).

Copper: copper is a natural product present in most food either as copper ions or copper salt (Codex 1955). It is an essential metal which is involved in the activities of the hemoglobin synthesis, bone and elastic tissue development, and the normal functioning of the central nervous system (Adestein and Vallee 1961). Its toxicity induces harmful impact on the primary production of plants and survival of plants. However, it is an essential metal for plant and involved in many metabolic processes in plant (Cambrollé et al 2015).

Cadmium: This is the least element detected in this study. Its value is within the permissible range. Cadmium is an essential element, it is also an important environmental pollutant present in soil, water and air. The toxicity of cadmium leads to cardiovascular disease, renal problem, emphysema, anosmia as reported by Lawal, Abdulahi, and Salisu (2020). The toxicity of cadmium in plant includes reduction in the uptake mechanism, translocation and increase in oxidative damage, disruption in plant metabolism and inhibits plant morphology and physiology. (Haider et al. 2021)

CONCLUSION

The concentration of heavy metal in coal and combust coal has been analyzed using AAS and the compared between both samples. In both sample Pb has the highest level of concentration followed by magnesium and chromium while the last three least elements are cobalt, copper and cadmium. For other elements determined, there is a difference in concentration in terms of position i.e. level of concentration. Findings indicated that for purpose of environmental and soil toxicity, lead whose value was higher in concentration is a very toxic substance to living organism even at low concentration. This indicates a great public health concern that should be address urgently especially in combust coal that is present in dump sites. Through bioaccumulation process, it can easily get to man and plant thereby leading to toxic effects. The underground water is also of great concern as its flows and not static as the case of soil. Through the soil, plants animals and humans can be contaminated result in issues of public health implications.

The disparity in the other element such as iron with more concentration in combust coal than coal as a matter fact the level of concentration in coal ash is far more than that in coal. The high concentration of lead in coal could be attribute to the fact that coal under goes some thermal processes before becoming combust coal and ultimately bottom coal ash and dumped in the coal reject site.

The present economic situation has resulted in people using various materials in the preparation of their food and other domestic activities. The use of coal in cooking and other domestic activities exposes humans to the lead inhalation. This has grave consequences to the health of people with serious public health implications. In developed countries, coal is also used during cold to warm homes. This expose people as well to the harmful effect of lead released in the process of thermal combustion of coal. This situation can also lead to issues of public health concerns.

It is thus important that the public health implications in the use of coal for domestic purposes be addressed as it has far-reaching public health implications.

We therefore suggest that further studies on the public health implications of the use of coal for domestic purposes be conducted to elucidate more public health implications associated with this practice. *To the best of our understanding this is the first time this study is carried out.*

ETHICAL STATEMENT

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

I I¹ : Author

O.A²: reviewed write up and made some contributions

V.O³ : reviewed write up and added her input

S.O⁴: helped in collection of combusted coal from Obajana

F D⁵: helped in collection of coal

All authors read and approved the manuscript

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS:

1. AAS: Atomic absorption spectrometer
2. WHO: World Health Organization
3. Cd: Cadmium
4. UN: united nation
5. DNA: deoxyribonucleic acid
6. Pb: Lead
7. Zn: Zinc
8. Fe: Iron
9. Mn: Manganese
10. Ni: Nickel
11. Cr: Chromium
12. Cu: Copper
13. Co: Cobalt
14. Magnesium

REFERENCE

1. Adestein S J and Vallee B L (1962); Mineral metabolism, copper, academic press, new york and London, page 371 PMID: 13859394 [https://doi: 10.1056/NEJM196111022651806](https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM196111022651806)
2. Afrid H, Solangi Q, Kazi T, Talpur F, BaigJ, Chanhoon G, and Channa G (2021): calcium and lead level in biological samples and their effect on the biochemical parameter of indoor and outdoor workers of five zonal area of coal mining field. American journal of analytical chemistry, 12, 260 -276. DOI: 10.4236/ajac.2021.126016
3. Andrade .M, Mateus M L, Batoriv M C, Aschner M, Marreilha, Dos Santos AP (2017); Toxic mechanism underlying motor activity changes induced by a mixture of lead, arsenic and manganese. *EC pharmacology and toxicology* 3.2:31-42
4. Barrow, N.J., Hartemink, A.E. The effects of pH on nutrient availability depend on both soils and plants. *Plant Soil* **487**, 21–37 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-023-05960-5>
5. Bifeng Hu, XiaolingJiehu (2017); Assessment of Heavy Metal Pollution and Health Risks in the Soil-Plant-Human System in the Yangtze River Delta, China. *International journal of environmental research and public health* Sep 10;14(9):1042 PMID: 28891954 [https://doi: 10.3390/ijerph14091042](https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14091042)
6. C.A. Adah , J. Abah, S.T. Ubwa, S. Ekele(2013); Soil Availability and Uptake of Some Heavy Metals by Three Staple Vegetables Commonly Cultivated along the South Bank of

- River Benue, Makurdi, Nigeria. Modern Scientific Press Company, Florida, USA
International Journal of Environment and Bioenergy, 8(2): 56-67
7. Cambrollé J, García JL, Figueroa ME, Cantos M. (2015): Evaluating wild grapevine tolerance to copper toxicity. Feb:120:171-8. [https://doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.06.044](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.06.044). Epub 2014 Jul 12
 8. Codex alimentarius (1195): international food standard, general standard for contaminant and toxins in food and feed. Cxs 193-1995
 9. Christos Noulas, Miltiadis Tziouvalekas, Theodore Karyotis (2018): Zinc in soils, water and food crops, Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology, Volume 49, Pages 252-260, ISSN 0946-672X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemb.2018.02.009>.
 10. Chen RJ, Lee VR. Cobalt Toxicity. [Updated 2023 Jul 29]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK587403/>
 11. Delno Knudsen (1974) G74-165 Understand Your Soil Test: Calcium, Magnesium, Boron, Copper, Chlorine, Molybdenum ; Historical Materials from University of Nebraska-Lincoln Extension,
 12. EARTH REPAIR: <https://earthrepair.ca/resources/scenarios/lead-remediation/> © 2023
 13. EPA(2023) : www.epa.gov.com
 14. Frankelman R. B , Dai s, French D (2019): the importance of mineral in coal as the host of chemical element : a review . International Journal of Coal Geology 212:103251 DOI:10.1016/j.coal.2019.103251
 15. Global Energy Monitor Wiki: www.gemwiki/okaba-coal-mine 23feb.2023
 16. Global energy monitors wiki. <https://www.gem.wiki/Chromium>
 17. Haider FU, Liqun C, Coulter JA, Cheema SA, Wu J, Zhang R, Wenjun M, Farooq M. (2021): Cadmium toxicity in plants: Impacts and remediation strategies. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf.* 2021 Mar 15;211:111887. [https://doi :10.1016/j.ecoenv.2020.111887](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2020.111887). Epub 2021 Jan 12. PMID: 33450535
 18. Jaishankar M, Tseten T, Anbalagan N, Mathew BB, Beeregowda KN. (2014) Toxicity, mechanism and health effects of some heavy metals. *InterdiscipToxicol.* 2014 Jun;7(2):60-72. Doi: 10.2478/intox-2014-0009.
 19. Jarup L (2013) Hazards of Metal Contamination.*British Medical Bulletin* 68(1):167-182
 20. Jeff Goodell(2006): Big coal: the dirty secret behind americans energy future. Newyork, N.Y : Houghton Mifflin
 21. Kabata- Pendias, A and Pendias, H (2010) trace elements in soils and plants.*3rd edition* , CRC press, Boca Raton. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1201/b10158>
 22. Koech L, Everson R, Neomagus H, Rutto H. (2015) Leaching kinetics of bottom ash waste as a source of calcium ions. *J Air Waste Manag Assoc.* 2015 Feb;65(2):126-32. [https://doi: 10.1080/10962247.2014.978958](https://doi.org/10.1080/10962247.2014.978958). PMID: 25947048
 23. Kusal K. Das R. Chandramouli Reddy, Ishwar B. Bagoji, Swastika Das, ShrilaxmiBagali, LataMullur, Jyoti P. Khodnapur and M.S. Biradar.(2018): Primary concept of nickel

- toxicity , Journal of Basic and Clinical Physiology and Pharmacology. <https://doi:10.1515/jbcpp-2017-0171>
24. Levi, S., Ripamonti, M., Moro, A.S. *et al.* Iron imbalance in neurodegeneration. *Mol Psychiatry* **29**, 1139–1152 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41380-023-02399-z>
 25. Lawal M A, Abdulahi A, Salisu A M (2020): Heavy metals in contaminated soil: source, accumulation, health risk and remediation process. *Bayero Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 14(1): 1 – 12. ISSN 2006 – 6996 <https://doi:10.4314/bajopas.v14i1.1>
 26. Mandal and Senqupta (2006), an assessment of soil contamination due to heavy metal around a coal fired thermal power plant in india. *Environmental geology* *51(1): 409-420*
 27. Mahey S, Kumar R., Sharma M. et al.(2020) A critical review on toxicity of cobalt and its bioremediation strategies.SN Appl. Sci. 2, 1279.<https://doi:10.1007/s42452-020-3020-9>
 28. M.O Aremo, B.O Atolaiye and L Labaran(201): Environmental Implication of Metal Concentrations in Soil, Plant Foods and Pond in Area around the Derelict Udege Mines of Nasarawa State; *Bull. Chem. Soc. Ethiop.* 2010, 24(3), 351-360. Chemical Society of Ethiopia 2010 <https://doi:10.4314/bcse.v24i3.60666>
 29. Musa D, Kpanache (2014) : the importance of obajana cement company as a grown pole in obajana k.s.nig. *ethiop.j. environ manage stud.* 2014;7(1):73-81 (cross ref) *googlescholar*
 30. P. Sankaralingam and P. Malarvizhi (2020): Fixation of critical level of available magnesium in soils of maize growing tracts of Pudukkottai district of Tamil Nadu, India. *Int.J.Curr.Microbiol.App.Sci.*2020.9(2):3017-3020 <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2020.902.346>
 31. Reeves, R.D. and Baker A.J.M. (2000): Metal accumulation in plants. In: *Phytoremediation of toxic metals: Using plant to clean up the environment.* (Ed: I. Raskin and B.D. Ensely). *John Wiley and Sons, Inc. Toronto, Canada.pp – 193-229*
 32. Speidel, H. and Speidel, M.O. *Metallurgy*(2002): High nickel release from 1- and euro at coins. *Nature* , 419:132.
 33. (TFI). The fertilizer institute : manganese essential element. www.tfi.org
 34. United nation (UN): global opportunity for reducing use of lead gasoline, IDMC/UNEP/CHEMICALS/98/9 Switzerland 1998
 35. Wuana R A and Okieimen F E (2011): Heavy Metals in Contaminated Soils: A Review of Sources, Chemistry, Risks and Best Available Strategies for Remediation. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 42, 111-122. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5402/2011/4026>
 36. Zahra N,Wahid A,Hafeez M B,Shaukat K, Uzzaman M H: iron toxicity in plant; impact and remediation. (2021) ,*physiol plant* 2021 sept. Volume 173(1) pp. 201-222. National library of medicine <https://doi: 10.1111/ppl.13361>.
 37. Zulfiqar U, Farooq M, Hussain S, Maqsood M, Hussain M, Ishfaq M, Ahmad M, Anjum MZ.(2019): Lead toxicity in plants: Impacts and remediation. *J Environ Manage.* Nov

15;250:109557. <https://doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.109557>. Epub 2019 Sep 26. PMID: 31545179.